

Improving indoor air quality by using photocatalytic paints. Real scale study at the Technical University of Madrid

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Indoor air quality
Photocatalytic paint
NO₂
Palmer passive sampler

ABSTRACT

People spend more than 90% of their time in indoor spaces, and, therefore, exposure to pollutants is high when inhabiting infrastructures with poor air quality. The pollutants present inside a building come either from inside the building itself (inhabitants, activity developed, etc), or from the outside (traffic, nearby industrial activity, etc). Among air cleaning techniques, building materials that incorporate a photocatalyst are considered to be a promising alternative. Photocatalysis is an Advanced Oxidation Process consisting of the oxidation/mineralization of pollutants in contact with a photocatalytic surface and the presence of UVA and sunlight irradiation. In this work, a photocatalytic paint based on TiO₂ and active under indoor illumination conditions (ProCleanAir®, by PROQUICESA S.L.) was tested in a lecture room, evaluating the concentration of NO₂ monitored by Palmer passive samplers. There was a decrease in the concentration of pollution after the application of the paint, with the depolluting effect remaining for one year, but also being dependent on atmospheric conditions. The statistical significance of the results was confirmed by *t*-student analyses.

1. Introduction

Indoor air pollution refers to the exposure to certain harmful substances that are present in houses, schools, hospitals, transports, etc. People spend more than 90% of their time in indoor spaces and, subsequently, their exposure level to these substances is particularly prolonged when inhabiting infrastructures with poor air quality. Pollutants present inside a building come either from inside the building (inhabitants, building materials, activity developed, etc), or from the outside (traffic, nearby industrial activity, etc). More than 900 substances have been identified in indoor air, and some of them can be up to 2–5 times more concentrated than outside. According to the European Lung White Book, indoor air pollution is the 8th most important risk factor for illness. The ‘Sick Building Syndrome’ (SBS) is the term used to describe the malaise experienced by people who live/work in buildings with poor air quality, and it is expressed through headaches, fatigue, or nausea, among other symptoms. It is estimated that around 30% of all buildings around the world suffer from this syndrome (Asociación

Ibérica de Fotocatálisis AIF and Almazán, 2020). In this context, photocatalysis arises as an alternative to improve the quality of air, both in indoor and outdoor spaces. Photocatalysis is an Advanced Oxidation Process consisting of the oxidation/mineralization of pollutants in contact with a photocatalytic surface and the presence of radiation that activates the photocatalyst, which is usually a semiconductor oxide. Photocatalysis has been widely tested at atmospheric pressure and room temperature, and although UVA is the preferred irradiation for activating the photocatalyst, solar radiation ($\approx 5\%$ UVA) has also been successfully applied. One of the most widely used photocatalysts in air purification processes, both indoors and outdoors, is titanium oxide (TiO₂) in its anatase and rutile varieties. This is due to thermal and chemical stability, covering power, and low acquisition cost (Chen et al., 2021) (Yu and Brouwers, 2009). In the case of NO_x, oxidation leads to the formation of NO₃⁻ ions through a process that occurs with a mechanism based on three stages and six reactions (Park and Cheol Choi, 2022) (Li et al., 2020):

Peer review under responsibility of Turkish National Committee for Air Pollution Research and Control.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apr.2023.101827>

Received 30 March 2023; Received in revised form 1 June 2023; Accepted 14 June 2023

Available online 16 June 2023

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- First step: NO_x adsorption onto TiO₂ surface photocatalyst
- Second step: NO_x oxidation

o *Electron and hole generation on the surface by the action of UV-VIS light*

o *Formation of hydroxyl radicals (strong oxidant) and superoxide anions on the surface*

o *NO_x oxidation to nitrate ions on the surface*

- Third step: Desorption, nitrate removal, and photocatalyst surface regeneration

With respect to the reaction (1) in the second step, the best type of irradiation is ultraviolet A (UVA), followed by sunlight or a light-emitting diode and ending with visible light or fluorescent light (Guo et al., 2017). On the other hand, as can be seen in the second step, the presence of oxygen and water is very important. The relative humidity is an important variable to control NO_x removal (Guo et al., 2012).

Since the last decade, many building materials have incorporated a photocatalyst in order to passively eliminate surrounding pollutants. Road pavements, floor tiles, cobbles, and roofs are examples of structures incorporating a photocatalyst for outdoor pollution reduction, while paints and coatings have been applied to treat indoor pollution. A major challenge regarding the control of air pollution is the fact that once the pollutants have been dispersed in the atmosphere, they are more difficult to abate than at their source of emission. The high volume (where pollutants are dispersed) to surface (where the photocatalyst is applied) ratio is a drawback in the application of this surface-based technology. However, many laboratory scale studies have been reported in the literature both for outdoor (Liu et al., 2013) (Devahadin et al., 2003) (Diamanti et al., 2008) (Folli et al., 2012) and indoor (Zhao and Yang, 2003) (Wang et al., 2007) (Zhihui Ai, Wingkei Ho, Shuncheng Lee, 2009) (Ao and Lee, 2005) applications with promising results. Standardized procedures are often employed in such studies in order to quantify the activity of the photocatalytic material. The Italian UNI 11259:2008, to test self-cleaning properties, the five international ISO 22197 (1–5) for NO_x, acetaldehyde, toluene, formaldehyde, and methyl-mercaptan, respectively, to test air purification capacity, and the ISO 27447:2009 to evaluate the bactericide effect are among the most currently used. In addition, a number of real-scale studies have been conducted mainly in the last decade. Most of these studies comprise laboratory scale tests under standardized conditions and the evaluation of the potentially better samples under real-scale conditions. In general, no strong evidence of a large depolluting effect of these materials was reported (usually below 30%), and given the complexity of the systems, it is often difficult to establish whether the changes observed are attributable to the presence of a photocatalyst or to natural reasons (Monks, 2016). However, important conclusions regarding the application procedure, maintenance, and washing have been derived from these projects, as well as simulation or material selection tools. Among these projects, most of them were focused on outdoor pollution, with PICADA (Guro, 2006), LIFE-Photoscaling (LIFE-PHOTOSCALING -, 2016), LIFE-Photopaq (Boonen et al., 2015), LIFE-Photocitytex (Soler, 2017), LIFE-Minoxstreet (Caballero, 2018), LIFE-Equinox (Fermoso, 2017), and Light2cat (CORDIS EU Research Results, 2015) being

notable. Regarding indoor pollution, it is worth noting ECO-SEE (Ling et al., 2017) and a project carried out in Greece that took place in two phases: first, in 2014, 1000 L of an Mn-doped TiO₂-based photocatalytic paint were applied to a road tunnel (Binás et al., 2021), and, in 2017, the paint was applied to the Medical Centre of Cadets in Crete (Maggos et al., 2019). In the first case, authors reported an invariant mechanical and photocatalytic performance after five years since the application of the paint, but no quantification of the results was reported. In addition, given the design of the experiment, no mirror or reference location was evaluated. In the second case, the study was conducted over a month, and both a reference and a test location were evaluated. However, only one result regarding the overall percentage of elimination after the month was reported, no reference to atmospheric conditions and outdoor concentrations was provided, and the final result was not supported by any statistical analysis. With this serving as context, we report a study in which the photocatalytic activity of a paint in terms of Indoor Air Quality is evaluated under the following basis: i) the concentration of NO₂ was measured prior to the application of the paint, ii) a test room and a reference room were simultaneously monitored during the work (>1 year), iii) the outdoor concentrations were considered, iv) atmospheric conditions (temperature and relative humidity) were considered, and v) statistical analyses to validate the significance of the results were applied. In addition, the accuracy of the measurements was validated with data obtained by chemiluminescence.

2. Experiment

Regarding location, the experiment was conducted at ETSIDI-UPM, which is situated in downtown Madrid, close to the traffic-regulated area of Madrid 360. However, heavy traffic is found all around the building, with there being a special build-up of it at the Ronda de Valencia façade. The location of the ETSIDI-UPM is shown in Fig. 1.

Two lecture rooms (namely A-17 and A-15) placed on the first floor of the building and facing Ronda de Valencia were selected, as shown in Fig. 2. A visible active mineral TiO₂-based photocatalytic paint (PRO-QUICESA S.L. PROCLEAN AIR®) was applied to A-17, and A-15 was used as a reference (mirror) room for comparison purposes. TiO₂ was doped with nitrogen compounds in order to induce a bathochromic shift in the absorption spectra, with the aim of promoting the photocatalytic effect in the presence of visible light, where the UVA radiation is scarce. The color of the paint was selected among the color range offered by the supplier, in order to keep the colors previously present in the rooms. The main color corresponded to RAL 9003 (signal white), with a baseboard in burgundy (RAL 4004).

Both rooms were identical in size (8.7 m × 9 m) and had the same distribution regarding windows, the blackboard, and the door, as well as a comparable academic activity. It should be noted that between both rooms there was another room (A-16), which was smaller in size (8.7 m × 5.4 m). The height of the room was 3 m in the three cases. These three rooms were connected by mobile walls, with the three of them either being isolated, connected, or one isolated and the other two connected, depending on schedule needs. Such configuration could not be controlled throughout the duration of the experiment, but it is assumed that in general, the two spaces (test and reference) were essentially comparable. In addition, an important feature to be highlighted is that, due to the COVID-19-derived sanitary protocols, all the windows were open all day long, or opened hourly for ventilation in the coldest seasons. This may have resulted in a larger transportation of outdoor (mainly traffic) pollutants inside the rooms.

The photocatalytic paint was applied on May 28th, 2021, with the measurements of the pollutants having been taken during the previous months.

NO₂ was monitored by the Palmes passive samplers, which were placed around each room. These samplers have a cylindrical shape (70 mm length, 11 mm diameter). One of the ends of the sampler is closed by a cap containing two metallic grids impregnated with a triethanolamine

- 1. ETSIDI-UPM
 - 2. Reina Sofía Art Museum
 - 3. Atocha train station
- — — — — Limit for traffic regulated zone

Fig. 1. Location of ETSIDI-UPM. Source: Cartography department. Madrid city council.

(TEA)-water 20/80 (v/v) solution. The other end is open, through which NO₂ diffuses by natural convection to reach the amine solution. Ten samplers were used in each room, with seven of them being placed inside and three being placed outside (windows' outer frames, as a reference of outdoor pollution), as shown in Fig. 3. Sampler tubes were collected after one week of exposure. The mass of NO₂ captured in each tube ($m_{\text{nitrite sampler}}$) was quantified by colorimetry using the Griess-Saltzman reaction, which is based on the formation of a chromophore compound associated with the formation of nitrites through the reaction of NO₂ with TEA that further reacts with a mixture of sulphanilamide and N-(1-naftil) ethylenediamine dichlorhydrate in acid medium. The color intensity related to the mass of NO₂ was measured by UV spectrophotometry at 540 nm (UV-Vis Perkin-Elmer Lambda 35). The concentration of NO₂ ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) in the air was calculated according to the following expression:

$$C_{\text{NO}_2} = \frac{m_{\text{nitrite sampler}}}{t_{\text{exposed}} \bullet S_{\text{rate}}} \quad (7)$$

Where $m_{\text{nitrite sampler}}$ corresponds to the mass of the nitrite, expressed in μg , t_{exposed} refers to the exposure time of the samplers in the room, expressed in s, and S_{rate} is the sampling rate, expressed in $\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$, which is, in turn, calculated according to:

$$S_{\text{rate}} = \frac{D_{12} \bullet a}{l} \quad (8)$$

Where a (m^2) and l (m) stand as the section and length of the sampler, respectively, and D_{12} ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) is the diffusivity of NO₂ in air, which depends on temperature according to the following equation (AEA Environment and Environment, 2008):

$$D_{12}(T) = D_{12}(273 \text{ K}) \bullet \left(\frac{T}{273 \text{ K}} \right)^{1.81} \quad (9)$$

The temperature at which D_{12} was calculated for outdoor measurements was taken from an Air Quality Control Station of Madrid City Council close to ETSIDI (Méndez Álvaro), while it was set at 22 °C for indoor measurements.

Five measurement campaigns of NO₂ concentration in the A-17 and A-15 rooms were conducted for more than a year as follows:

- The first measurement campaign was conducted for three weeks prior to the application of the paint, between March 10th and April 8th, 2021.
- The second measurement campaign was conducted for three weeks right after the application of the paint, between June 4th and 25th, 2021.
- The third measurement campaign was conducted for six weeks, five months after the application of the paint, between October 13th and November 24th, 2021.
- The fourth measurement campaign was conducted for four weeks, ten months after the application of the paint, between April 1st and May 3rd, 2022.
- The fifth measurement campaign was conducted for two weeks, more than twelve months after the application of the paint, June 8th-15th and 21st-28th, 2022.

In parallel to the measurements of the first campaign (prior to the application of the paint), a set of measurements were taken in order to validate the accuracy of the data provided by the Palmes passive

Fig. 2. Location of the test and reference rooms on the first floor of ETSIDI. Source: Subdirectorate of Infrastructures and Economic Affairs (ETSIDI-UPM).

Fig. 3. Location of the Palmes passive samplers in the test (A-17) and reference (A-15) rooms.

samplers. With this purpose, four tubes were located on the rooftop of the Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales (ETSII-UPM), collecting and measuring the NO₂ concentration levels each week for five consecutive weeks from March 9th to April 13th, 2021. ETSII-UPM is located in Paseo de la Castellana, with a distance below 100 m from the Air Quality Station Castellana of Madrid City Council (Madrid City Hall, 2021). Data provided by this station were obtained through a chemiluminescence analysis, with this being the standard and most

reliable technique for the measurement of NO₂. This information was retrieved as hourly NO₂ concentration and averaged to the duration of the measurement campaign. These data were compared with the data obtained with the Palmes passive samplers. *t*-student statistical analyses were applied to the results, assuming a normal distribution, in order to evaluate the statistical significance of the concentration differences observed between the test and reference rooms. It should be noted that the illumination of rooms, when used, had standard LED 32 W, 4000k

luminaries, 600 × 600 mm (Silvania). This illumination was not controlled, but used as needed by the users of the rooms.

3. Results

3.1. Validation of measurements

Firstly, the accuracy of the NO₂ concentration values was assessed in comparison to the concentrations provided by the Air Quality Station Castellana of Madrid City Council. Table 1 shows the corresponding results. It must be noted that the average values obtained for the five measurement campaigns spanned the range of 16.8–49.0 µg/m³, according to our measurements, and 15.7–45.7 µg/m³, according to the Air Quality Station. These values show a large dependence on atmospheric and traffic conditions, overcoming the annual limit value (40 µg/m³) in one of the campaigns, as established by Spanish Air Quality regulations (RD 102/2011, (BOE, 2011)). The standard deviation calculated for the four measurements with the Palmes passive samplers was lower than 1 µg/m³ in three out of the five campaigns, with 2.3 µg/m³ being the highest value. This corresponds to coefficients of variation ≤6.1%, which can be taken as a low dispersion. A trend between the dispersion and average concentration values cannot be established.

A very good correspondence between our measurements and those provided by the City Council's station is demonstrated, with percentage differences lower than 11% in all the cases, and lower than 8% in three out of the five campaigns. In addition, mean values obtained with the passive samplers were higher than those obtained by chemiluminescence in four out of the five campaigns.

3.2. First and second campaigns

Table 2 shows the mean NO₂ concentrations measured with the Palmes passive samplers in the test (A-17) and reference (A-15) rooms during the weeks before and after the application of the paint, together with the percentage of removal and the *p*-values derived from the *t*-student statistical analyses conducted. These analyses were done to pairs of data series for the test and reference rooms, respectively, in order to elucidate whether the differences observed between NO₂ concentrations in both rooms are statistically significant. The significance of the test was set at 0.05. This indicates that whenever *p*-values are <0.05, the two series under comparison are statistically different. Values corresponding to outdoor concentrations were in the range of 33–54 µg/m³, that is, close to or above the annual limit value (40 µg/m³) established by Spanish Air Quality regulations (RD 102/2011). These values were slightly higher for the test than for the reference room in four out of the six weeks reported, and the statistical analyses revealed that these differences were not statistically significant in the first four campaigns, significant but close to the limit of significance in the fifth week, and only strongly significant in the sixth week (with a higher concentration in the test room). Leaving aside the sixth week, the outdoor concentration was similar for both rooms. These outdoor values set a proper framework in order to evaluate the effect of the photocatalytic paint inside the rooms. Values measured indoors were lower, generally below 30 µg/m³ and only in one case above 40 µg/m³. However, such

concentrations are not negligible (never below 23 µg/m³), and a sound decrease would mean a contribution towards improving indoor air quality. During the three weeks before the application of the paint, no appreciable differences in NO₂ indoor concentrations were observed between the test and reference rooms. The statistical analyses revealed that the differences were not significant in two out of the three cases, with the concentration being higher in the test room in the case where statistical significance was encountered. This trend consistently changed for indoor measurements upon application of the photocatalytic paint. The three following weeks were consistent with regard to a lower NO₂ concentration in the test room, and the statistical analyses consistently indicated that differences were significant. The activity of the paint, as a % of removal of the pollutant, was calculated as the percentage difference in mean pollutant concentration between the reference and test room in the same period, according to the following expression:

$$\%_{NO_2} = \frac{[NO_2]_{ref} - [NO_2]_{test}}{[NO_2]_{ref}} \times 100 \quad (10)$$

For this period, the percentage of NO₂ removal was in the range of 12.1–29.5.

3.3. Third campaign

With the same structure as Table 2, Table 3 shows the results obtained over six weeks, five months after the application of the photocatalytic paint. Focusing first on the outdoor concentrations, and similar to those obtained in the previous campaigns, the mean concentration values were very similar outside both rooms. No statistically significant differences were observed in any of the cases (only in the fourth week the *p*-value was in the limit of significance; 0.05). However, analyzing the indoor concentrations, important differences were observed. NO₂ mean concentration values were, in the six cases, lower in the test room, being the measured differences statistically significant in four out of the six weeks (weeks one to four), with a percentage of removal in the range of 9.4–17.5. Week five recorded a very poor performance, with only 1.3% of removal and a subsequent high value of *p* statistic; 0.74. Week six, in turn, recorded a better performance, with more than 10% of removal, although the *p*-value was threefold the limit of significance.

3.4. Fourth campaign

The mean concentration values obtained over four weeks, ten months after the application of the paint, are summarized in Table 4. Again, the values measured outdoors did not show any significant differences between both rooms, and only in the first week was the *p*-value below the limit of significance, with a higher concentration outside the test room. This trend switched for the same week when measuring the indoor concentration, with above 25% of removal, which remained (with larger removal percentages; 30.2 and 33.3 respectively, and lower *p*-values) in the second and fourth weeks. Only in the third week was a slightly higher concentration measured in the test room, with there being a negative percentage of removal calculated and a high *p*-value.

Table 1

Comparison of NO₂ concentration values obtained by the Palmer samplers and chemiluminescence (Castellana Air Quality Station of Madrid City Council).

Date (2021)	NO ₂ concentration rooftop (µg/m ³)	Standard deviation (µg/m ³)	Coefficient of variation (%)	NO ₂ concentration City Council (µg/m ³)	% difference
March 9–12	37.1	2.3	6.1	33.5	10.83
March 16–22	16.8	0.8	4.7	15.7	6.48
March 22–26	49.0	1.5	3.0	45.7	7.14
March 30–April 6	22.2	0.5	2.2	22.8	–2.56
April 6–13	24.6	0.8	3.4	22.3	10.42

Table 2
Average NO₂ concentration, percentage of removal, and *p*-values (significance = 0.05) associated with the test and reference rooms (inside and outside). First and second campaigns. n.a. stands for not applicable.

	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.
A-17	28.3	n.a.	27.3	28.1	33.3	29.7	21.8	29.5	21.8	20.1
A-15	28.9	n.a.	23.6	27.6	37.9	42.1	27.5	29.5	27.5	In ^a
<i>P</i>	0.27		9.20·10 ⁻⁶	0.27	1.10·10 ⁻⁴	2.30·10 ⁻¹⁰	1.80·10 ⁻⁵		1.80·10 ⁻⁵	
A-17	37.3	n.a.	37.0	44.3	53.3	52.3	40.3	n.a.	40.3	n.a.
A-15	38.0	n.a.	36.0	44.0	50.3	53.7	33.2	n.a.	33.2	Out ^b
<i>P</i>	0.33		0.11	0.37	0.18	0.04	7.80·10 ⁻⁵		7.80·10 ⁻⁵	
	10-17 Mar		17-24 Mar	24 Mar-8 Apr	4-11 Jun	11-18 Jun	18-25 Jun		18-25 Jun	

^a Average of the seven tubes placed inside each room.

^b Average of the three tubes placed outside each room.

Table 3

Average NO₂ concentration, percentage of removal, and *p*-values (significance = 0.05) associated with the test and reference rooms (inside and outside). Third campaign. n.a. stands for not applicable.

	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% elim.
A-17	43.8	14.3	31.1	31.5	27.8	38.0	31.3	1.3	34.9	10.3
A-15	51.1		36.5	38.2	30.7	38.5	0.15		0.15	
<i>P</i>	3.56·10 ⁻⁵		0.017	0.014	0.03	0.74	54.1	n.a.	54.1	n.a.
A-17	74.8	n.a.	56.5	57.0	48.8	58.2	49.7	n.a.	49.7	Out ^b
A-15	73.1	n.a.	57.0	54.6	44.8	62.0	0.02	n.a.	0.02	
<i>P</i>	0.26		0.66	0.38	0.05	0.17	17-24 Nov		17-24 Nov	
	13-20 Oct		20-27 Oct	27 Oct-3 Nov	3-10 Nov	10-17 Nov				

^a Average of the seven tubes placed inside each room.

^b Average of the three tubes placed outside each room.

Table 4

Average NO₂ concentration, percentage of removal, and *p*-values (significance = 0.05) associated with the test and reference rooms (inside and outside). Fourth campaign. n.a. stands for not applicable.

	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	
A-17	14.9		13.0		15.8		12.2		
A-15	19.9	25.1	18.6	30.2	15.6	-1.2	18.3	33.3	In ^a
<i>p</i>	0.05		0.0006		0.94		0.003		
A-17	21.5		23.1		25.2		24.2		
A-15	19.3	n.a.	26.2	n.a.	22.9	n.a.	26.2	n.a.	Out ^b
<i>p</i>	0.01		0.24		0.35		0.29		
	1-8 Apr		8-19 Apr		19-26 Apr		26 Apr-3 May		

^a Average of the seven tubes placed inside each room.

^b Average of the three tubes placed outside each room.

Table 5

Average NO₂ concentration, percentage of removal, and *p*-values (significance = 0.05) associated with test and reference rooms (inside and outside). Fifth campaign. n.a. stands for not applicable.

	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	[NO ₂] (µg/m ³)	% rem.	
A-17	20.5		18.6		
A-15	32.8	37.5	28.7	35.2	In ^a
<i>p</i>	1.56·10 ⁻⁹		1.93·10 ⁻⁶		
A-17	39.1		26.5		
A-15	41.0	n.a.	27.0		Out ^b
<i>p</i>	0.49		0.66		
	8-15 Jun		21-27 Jun		

^a Average of the seven tubes placed inside each room.

^b Average of the three tubes placed outside each room.

3.5. Fifth campaign

Finally, NO₂ concentrations were analyzed over two weeks, one year after the application of the paint. As in the previous campaigns, Table 5 shows negligible differences in the outdoor concentrations, while results corresponding to indoor measurements show that the paint had a significant effect in the test room, with percentages of removal higher than 35% in both cases and strong statistical significance of the differences observed.

4. Discussion

Once the statistical significance of the differences observed upon the application of the photocatalytic paint had been noted, the following ideas arose:

First, it is important to establish to what extent the application of the paint was successful, in other words, to quantify the activity of the paint. The nature of the experiments makes it impossible to know what would have been the concentration of pollutants in the same room, under identical conditions, and without the photocatalytic paint. However, the reference room stands as a good benchmark. This activity, as % of removal of NO₂, was calculated according to equation (10).

A straightforward comparison with the majority of works reported in the literature cannot be done, since they are usually performed under controlled laboratory conditions. More interesting is the comparison with real-scale projects conducted in the last years, as commented in the introductory section, despite most of them being focused on outdoor applications.

The pioneering PICADA project (2002–2005) reported “significant” reductions in NO_x when applying TiO₂ on building façades and roads in Italy. The large surface-to-volume ratio employed in the real-scale experiments (street canyon) may stand as a drawback in terms of scalability when analyzing these results. LIFE PhotoPaq project (2010–2014) reported a discrete reduction of NO_x when applying TiO₂ in cementitious materials on side walls and the ceiling of an illuminated tunnel in Brussels, Belgium, and observed a strong deactivation of the

photocatalyst. The Light2Cat project (2012–2015) developed improved photocatalysts for a better use of solar light in non-Mediterranean countries and applied them to concretes. A reduction in the range of 5–20% in the concentration of NO_x was reported. The LIFE EquiNOx project (2013–2017) applied TiO₂ to asphalt pavements in the city of Madrid, Spain. The results reported were assumed as non-concluding and NO_x removals were lower than 25% (up to 42% under certain conditions). The PhotoCityTex project (2014–2017) tested photocatalytic textiles for outdoor applications in Valencia, Spain. An NO reduction of up to 80–90% in 30 min without an appreciable deactivation under controlled conditions (EUPHORE camera) was reported, while this percentage strongly decreased for real site tests (50 and 30% in the school and the tunnel, respectively). LIFE MINOX-Street (2013–2018) applied TiO₂ to façades, pavements, and sidewalks in Madrid (Spain). This project thoroughly studied commercially-available photocatalytic materials and reported NO_x reduction efficiencies from 30 to 10% after two years of usage. A proper washing of the surfaces where the photocatalyst was applied strongly improved its efficiency. LIFE Photoscaling (2014–2019) was further focused on the sustainability of applying the photocatalytic technology to construction materials in urban areas and created a decision-maker tool that takes into account all the aspects concerning this technology, i.e. chemical and mechanical performance and potential secondary effects (Jimenez-Relinque et al., 2020). The NO_x reduction measured achieved 30%. This particular project employed the same Palmes passive samplers as the present study, and field experiments were conducted in the streets surrounding ETSIDI-UPM. Regarding the projects focused on indoor conditions, in the work conducted in the Medical Centre of Cadets in Crete, an overall NO reduction of 18.8% was reported. Although NO_x does not primarily originate in indoor facilities, those buildings located in places highly exposed to traffic, like big cities, and mainly during periods when windows remain open, are subjected to a non-negligible concentration of this pollutant. Fig. 4 shows the temporal evolution of the performance of the photocatalytic paint during the first year of the project. Data are weekly averaged, as collected during the five measurement campaigns. It must be noted that no repainting or washing operations were done during this time. With the exception of two out of the fifteen weeks analyzed, the removal percentages spanned the range of 9.4–37.5%, with a total average value of 19.4%. Even if NO₂ and NO degradation cannot be directly compared, it is worth mentioning the work of Maggos et al. (2019), where they reported 18.8% NO degradation in a real-scale experiment. It is observed that no temporal decline in pollution removal activity was observed, which suggests that deactivation or saturation of photoactive sites did not occur to an important extent during the first year. Rather, a cyclic pattern—attributable to atmospheric conditions—could be observed. It must be taken into account that although measurements were conducted indoors, given the sanitary conditions derived from COVID-19, windows remained open for long periods, or were opened hourly for ventilation purposes during coldest or warmest days.

Despite the trend not being linear (taking into account the multiple factors affecting such a real-scale experiment), there is a good agreement

Fig. 4. Percentages of removal of NO₂ (bars, left axis). Weekly averaged temperature (dashed line, left axis) and relative humidity (continuous line, right axis). Source: Open data web. Madrid City Council.

between higher photocatalytic activity and those periods with higher temperature and lower relative humidity. On the one hand, higher temperature correlates with higher irradiance and a subsequent higher activation of the photoactive sites. On the other hand, while water is very important for photocatalysis (needed to generate OH* radicals, as shown in the introduction section), water vapor can compete with the photocatalyst active sites, mainly when the pollutant is present at the ppb level (Maggos et al., 2007), as is the case of our study. These results agree with the report by Cordero et al. in a work derived from the LIFE Photoscaling project (Cordero et al., 2021) (Cordero et al., 2020).

According to the above, the efficiencies obtained in this study have good agreement with those reported for outdoor application in other real-scale experiences, despite the obvious differences in terms of flow and dispersion conditions between indoor and outdoor sites.

4. Conclusions

The results presented above confirm a positive effect of applying photocatalytic paint on indoor air quality. The concentration of NO₂ decreased upon the application of the paint in the range of 9.4–37.5%, and this change was confirmed by the statistical analyses. A seasonal pattern in pollution removal activity was observed, measuring larger NO₂ abatement in periods with higher temperatures and lower relative humidity. Even if the removal percentages reported are not high enough to be considered as a unique and definite tool for the abatement and control of atmospheric pollutants, it should be considered as a part of a multitask solution, with there still being plenty of room for further real scale tests that take into account the conclusions from the present study and that consider other kinds of locations and scales.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Antonio Nieto-Márquez: Conceptualization, Formal analysis,

Supervision, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition. Manuel de Mateo: Investigation, Data curation. Andrea Barrios: Investigation, Data curation. M del Mar de la Fuente: Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. Adolfo Narros: Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Antonio Nieto-Marquez reports financial support and equipment, drugs, or supplies were provided by Proquicesa S.L.

Acknowledgments

Authors gratefully acknowledge ESTIDI-UPM Subdirectorate of Infrastructures and Economic Affairs for facilitating the development of the project, and to PROQUICESA for providing the ProClean Air® photocatalytic paint in ETSIDI.

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